

AWARENESS OF DIGITAL MARKETING PRACTICES ON RURAL AREAS COLLEGE STUDENTS OF CHHATTISGARH

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ABSTRACT:

The term Awareness of marketing practices and perception is very important in current scenario for all. Digital Marketing is the advance form of buying and selling of goods and services through the virtual world with the use of information technology and artificial Intelligence. This studies is concerned Govt. T.C.L. P.G. Colleges Janjgir of Chhattisgarh. This study is based on primary data with 130 Sample size. Mixed format schedule and interview technique used for the study. Awareness and perceptions of Digital marketing of respondents are differs them according to need, quality, price, status, income level, etc. Social media play vital role as a factors affecting for digital marketing. Web Access Design has been significant role as Perceptions of digital marketing. The perceptions of the college students have been changing in a faster rate with the change in time about digital marketing.

KEYWORDS:

DIGITAL MARKETING, AWARENESS, PERCEPTION, HIGHER EDUCATION.

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INTRODUCTION

Our country is highly populated country. Majority of the Indian population lives in the rural areas. Purchasing power of the rural people has been increased significantly in the recent past. Awareness of the rural people also increased significantly. Digital Marketing is the advance form of buying and selling of goods and services through the virtual world. With the use of information technology, and artificial Intelligence big bagger of the globe are attaching with their prospected customers through the virtual platform. 'GO RURAL' is the mantra for almost all marketers in India nowadays (M Dhanyashree (2023)). Digital Marketing has emerged as extra well-known after the involvement of modern technologies in businesses. It has completely changed the historic advertising methods and compelled marketers to remain linked with their buyers or clients by using the net for promoting their products and services (D. Poorani 2021). Digital marketing has emerged as a powerful tool for businesses to expand their reach and engage with their target audience in the digital age. The state of Chhattisgarh, located in central India, has witnessed significant advancements in technology and internet connectivity in recent years (Shrivastava 2023) there are need to in-depth investigation is required to uncover the intricacies of rural women's online shopping behaviors, the influence of

digital marketing and potential strategies to enhance their e-commerce experiences (M. Krishnaveni 2024.) Covid-19 pandemic carried disaster and stop the pulse of the globe in various ways such as declining production, transportation system, Movement of human being and many more. But the only thing that has taken great advantage to overcome the crisis is Digital world i.e. digitalisation. Digitalisation is the process to add digital technology in the life of human being in different forms (pradhan2022). In the same way Awareness and perception of digital marketing practices on rural areas college students of Chhattisgarh subject choose for the study. Special reference to Janjgir–Champa District of Chhattisgarh.

OBJECTIVES –

- To know the Awareness of marketing practices in rural areas college students.
- To analyze the perception of students towards Digital Marketing.

NEED FOR THE STUDY –

In the rapidly evolving landscape of higher education in India, digital marketing strategies have become pivotal tools for institutions aiming to enhance visibility, attract prospective students, and maintain competitive advantage.

However, the effectiveness of these strategies in achieving these objectives and their impact on the sector's ability to construct and communicate quality knowledge remains underexplored. This study seeks to investigate how digital marketing strategies are currently employed by Indian higher education institutions, their impact on enrollment numbers and student acquisition, and their role in shaping perceptions of educational quality and relevance in the digital age.

LIMITATION –

This study is limited to Govt. T.C.L. P.G. Colleges Janjgir of Chhattisgarh, which is oldest institute in region in the field of higher education. So it is representation entire area of the region. The college is located in rural areas.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE –

Madhulika A. (2025) findings reveal a significant skew towards younger respondents (20-40 years) and male participants. While a majority of respondents have a graduation degree and fall within the middle income bracket (₹20,000-₹40,000), a considerable proportion are students. The study indicates a strong correlation between digital marketing awareness and factors such as age, education, internet usage, tech savviness, social media engagement, online shopping behavior, search engine usage, and exposure to digital advertising. Respondents with higher levels of education, tech-savviness, and engagement with online platforms demonstrated greater awareness of digital marketing strategies.

Krishnaveni M & K.Umameswari (2024) Findings that an in-depth investigation is required to uncover the intricacies of rural women's online shopping behaviors, the influence of digital marketing and potential strategies to enhance their e-commerce experiences.

Pradhan P (2024) In last few years the trend of buying pattern has drastically increased and the cash less economy and urbanisation funda has boost the model to high rank in India. The perceptions of the college students have been changing in a faster rate with the change in time. In this paper at attempt is made to explain the buying factors that affect the buying pattern of the College students under the study area.

M Dhanyashree (2023) This paper describes the present scenario of rural digital market and explores the challenges and potential opportunities businesses have with the companies going rural with digital marketing. The study comes to the conclusion that the need for and use of digital marketing will continuously grow in rural area.

Saravanan Ravi & others. (2023) The Review provides a literature review of who is willing to use digital marketing over traditional marketing.

Shrivastava P & others (2023) This research paper aims to provide an overview of the current state of digital marketing in Chhattisgarh, explore the opportunities it presents, and analyze the challenges faced by businesses in adopting and implementing digital marketing strategies.

Ignatius Inpa Rajathi. & Arockiadass. A (2022), According to the poll, students' knowledge of particular digital marketing strategies varies. Gender disparities persist even when social media exposure exposes users to a variety of online marketing tactics. Women typically know more about topics like spotting deceptive marketing and the impact of reviews. Students' platform of choice seems to have an impact on how aware they are of particular marketing strategies.

Poorani, D., et al.(2021) This research offers some of the options to overcome the problems and analyzing the satisfactory method in a present-day scenario in the discipline and suggests directions for future development.

METHODOLOGY –

This is discreptive type and primary data based study. sample size is 130 students. Mixed format schedule and interview technique used for the study. Data collected by quarterly sequences (like 1-4-8) based for post graduate level students of different stream. Percentage method has been used to analyse data.

DISCUSSION AND RESULT –

This study has been completed in six stages as a basis of education stream, gender, Right marketing practices, source of knowledge of product, knowledge of marketing strategy, Factors influencing of digital marketing and Perceptions of digital marketing which is below as table wise –

1. EDUCATION STREAM OF RESPONDENTS –

In this portion identified that all randomly selected respondents are belong to various streams like Commerce, science, Art, Law which is mainly courses offered by institute. These are mention below as table no.1

TABLE-1
EDUCATION STREAM OF RESPONDENTS

S.N.	Stream	No. of students	% in total
01	Science	41	31
02	Commerce	32	25
03	Art	35	27
04	Law	22	17
Total		130	100

Source- primary data

It is maximum no. of 41 respondents are science background, whereas 22 respondents belong to law stream.

2. GENDER OF RESPONDENTS –

Under this head classified the boys and girls who are randomly selected for the study on the basis of gender. Details below as table no. 02

TABLE-2
GENDER OF RESPONDENTS

S.N.	Stream	No. of students boys	% in total	No. of students Girls	% in total
01	Science	22	34	19	29
02	Commerce	17	27	15	23
03	Art	13	21	22	33
04	Law	12	19	10	15
Total		64	100	66	100

Source- primary data

This table has been shows that maximum boys belongs science stream, where as girls belongs Art group. As well as minimum both respondents are regarding Law stream.

3. RIGHT MARKETING PRACTICES –

This head we included that respondents priority factor of choice for purchasing items, like brand name, Price, Utility, and others like quality, fashion which is mention below Table-3

TABLE-3

RIGHT MARKETING PRACTICES

S.N.	Priority	No. of students Boys	% in total	No. of students Girls	% in total
01	Price	17	27	13	20
02	Brand	13	20	12	18
03	Utility	13	20	22	33
04	Others	21	33	19	29
Total		64	100	66	100

Source- primary data

Under this table clear that maximum boys and girls belongs others priority head, whereas brand is lower options this head. Although boys priority both brand and utility also.

4. SOURCES OF KNOWLEDGE OF PRODUCT –

This portion some basic sources has been included for the study like, E-Resources, T.V., News paper, and other sources , which is mention below table -4

TABLE-4
SOURCES OF KNOWLEDGE OF PRODUCT

S.N.	Sources	No. of students Boys	% in total	No. of students Girls	% in total
01	e-resource	22	34	18	27
02	T.V.	12	19	15	23
03	News paper	13	20	20	30
04	Others	17	27	13	20
Total		64	100	66	100

Source- primary data

According to table's e-resources is major source for knowledge of product. T.V. for boys and others for girls is lowest source.

5. FACTORS INFLUENCING OF DIGITAL MARKETING –

In this title we concluded which factors that may be influenced digital transaction, which is mention below table no.05

TABLE-5

FACTORS INFLUENCING OF DIGITAL MARKETING

S.N.	Factors	No. of students Boys	% in total	No. of students Girls	% in total
01	Social Media	26	41	30	45
02	Advertisement	13	20	16	24
03	Informative Videos	10	16	17	26
04	Others	15	23	03	05
Total		64	100	66	100

Source- primary data

Table shows that social media is play main role rather than other factors.

6. PERCEPTIONS OF DIGITAL MARKETING –

This segment we concluded that matter influenced for digital transaction here consider as a perception of digital marketing. Table no. 06 shows details below as-

TABLE- 06

PERCEPTIONS OF DIGITAL MARKETING

S.N.	Base of Perceptions	No. of students Boys	% in total	No. of students Girls	% in total
01	Web access Design	22	34	16	25
02	Quick method of buying	18	28	14	21
03	Transaction Time and Safety	11	18	18	27
04	Others	13	20	18	27
Total		64	100	66	100

Source- primary data

Above table clear that Web access Design most base of perception for boys, whereas Transaction Time and Safety and others for girls. Rather than rest base.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS –

This studies finding that mojour four streams are run in the college, which is a science stream student are actively participated for study .in which Girls are more than boys which indicated no barrier of gender for such marketing practices. under the right marketing practices there are no single matter of brand for choice .price, utility also play role in digital marketing. E- Resources is most credible platform perform for knowledge of source. AS well as Social media play vital role as a factors affecting for digital marketing. Whereas Web Access Design has been significant role as Perceptions of digital marketing.

This study limited to lead college of the Janjgir–Champa district of Chhattisgarh, this study can be further continue for more knowledge and credibility in wide range for society awareness. It can be included as suggestions.

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